

Appendix 1

A list containing information on cadastral areas, their affiliation to administrative units, and the source of the digitized index sketches from the website of the Moravian Provincial Archives in Brno¹, Fund D9 (available online by 13-06-2025).

Cadastral area	Estate	Signature (sign.)	Year	Index sketch source
Bohuslavice nad Vlčí	Brumov I	144	1828	https://www.mza.cz/indikacniskici/skica/detail/223
Brumov	Brumov I	240	1828	https://www.mza.cz/indikacniskici/skica/detail/355
Bylnice	Brumov I	86	1828	https://www.mza.cz/indikacniskici/skica/detail/142
Drnovice	Brumov I	506	1828	https://www.mza.cz/indikacniskici/skica/detail/731
Francova Lhota	Brumov I	547	1828	https://www.mza.cz/indikacniskici/skica/detail/793
Haluzice	Brumov II	634	1828	https://www.mza.cz/indikacniskici/skica/detail/915
Horní Lideč	Brumov II	743	1828	https://www.mza.cz/indikacniskici/skica/detail/1058
Jestřabí	Brumov I	905	1828	https://www.mza.cz/indikacniskici/skica/detail/1307
Křekov	Brumov I	1127	1828	https://www.mza.cz/indikacniskici/skica/detail/1615
Lačnov	Brumov I	1214	1828	https://www.mza.cz/indikacniskici/skica/detail/1755
Leskovec	Brumov I	1252	1829	https://www.mza.cz/indikacniskici/skica/detail/1808
Lidečko	Brumov I	1295	1828	https://www.mza.cz/indikacniskici/skica/detail/1862
Lipina	Brumov I	1304	1828	https://www.mza.cz/indikacniskici/skica/detail/1874
Loučka	Brumov II	1352	1828	https://www.mza.cz/indikacniskici/skica/detail/1944
Lužná	Brumov I	1395	1829	https://www.mza.cz/indikacniskici/skica/detail/1998
Mírošov	Brumov I	1541	1828	https://www.mza.cz/indikacniskici/skica/detail/2212
Návojná	Brumov III	1632	1828	https://www.mza.cz/indikacniskici/skica/detail/2351
Nedašov	Brumov I	1642	1828	https://www.mza.cz/indikacniskici/skica/detail/2372
Nedašova Lhota	Brumov I	1643	1828	https://www.mza.cz/indikacniskici/skica/detail/2375
Popov	Brumov I	2023	1828	https://www.mza.cz/indikacniskici/skica/detail/2860
Poteč	Brumov I	2046	1828	https://www.mza.cz/indikacniskici/skica/detail/2894
Pulčín	Brumov I	2130	1828	https://www.mza.cz/indikacniskici/skica/detail/3022
Slopné	Brumov II	2441	1828	https://www.mza.cz/indikacniskici/skica/detail/3455
Smolína	Brumov I	2445	1828	https://www.mza.cz/indikacniskici/skica/detail/3464
Střelná	Brumov I	2566	1828	https://www.mza.cz/indikacniskici/skica/detail/3637
Štítná nad Vlčí	Brumov I	2543	1828	https://www.mza.cz/indikacniskici/skica/detail/3599
Študlov	Brumov III	2590	1828	https://www.mza.cz/indikacniskici/skica/detail/3668
Tichov	Brumov I	362	1828	https://www.mza.cz/indikacniskici/skica/detail/535
Újezd u Valašských Klobouk	Brumov I	1882	1828	https://www.mza.cz/indikacniskici/skica/detail/2679
Valašská Polanka	Brumov I	2007	1828	https://www.mza.cz/indikacniskici/skica/detail/2836
Valašská Senice	Brumov II	2382	1828	https://www.mza.cz/indikacniskici/skica/detail/3373
Valašské Klobouky	Brumov I	2798	1828	https://www.mza.cz/indikacniskici/skica/detail/3965
Valašské Příkazy	Brumov III	2085	1828	https://www.mza.cz/indikacniskici/skica/detail/2956
Vlachova Lhota	Brumov II	2927	1828	https://www.mza.cz/indikacniskici/skica/detail/4141
Vlachovice	Brumov I	2929	1828	https://www.mza.cz/indikacniskici/skica/detail/4145
Vrbětice	Brumov II	2975	1828	https://www.mza.cz/indikacniskici/skica/detail/4217
Vysoké Pole	Brumov I	3000	1828	https://www.mza.cz/indikacniskici/skica/detail/4256

¹ Moravian Provincial Archives in Brno. <https://www.mza.cz/>